

Development and Implementation of Online Health Services System

An Adaptive Barangay Information System

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ABSTRACT

Barangay Health Services has been providing assistance throughout its premise ever since the release of the Letter of Instruction No. 949, s. 1979 by President Ferdinand Marcos mandating the minister of health to develop and implement programs focusing on health development at the community level. This has caused barangay officials to collaborate and create a team of barangay health workers with nurses and midwives that will be able to provide such services for each individuals and families. Thus, in the ever-changing world where technology penetrates in all aspects of human interaction, it is essential to have an automated information system for barangay health services as well. Though the grounds for making such progress were not limited to what one community is using, it is ideal for one barangay health services clinic to work together with the others and be united at its core. This study proposes the development and implementation of an online health services system that will be able to serve its function for the barangays of San Mateo Rizal. It is meant to be user-system adaptive considering the process flows and reports mandated by the Municipal Health office and the Department of Health.

KEYWORDS

BHW, Adaptability, Barangay, User-System Adaptability, FHSIS

1 INTRODUCTION

In 1999, the Department of Health underwent an organizational reform and launched Interlocal Health Zones (ILHZ) enjoining municipalities in optimizing resources and maximizing benefits from local health services. This motion is supported by the Republic Act No. 7160 of 1991 which states that local government units shall ensure and support, among other things, the preservation and enrichment of culture, promote health and safety, enhance the right of the people to a balanced ecology, encourage and support the development of appropriate and self-reliant scientific and technological capabilities and the like. In which, embarking LGUs to handle the general welfare of its jurisdiction to preserve the comfort and convenience. Thus, developing an infrastructure or spearheading the improvement of their existing processes is upon their purview.

The online health services system identified different business opportunities such as patient health records, profile and security, less rework on document and reports, support in health care delivery and administration, prompt data availability for decision making in the barangay health services level, adaptable information system to support the transactions through the barangay health workers,

sufficiency and efficiency of barangay health workers and increase in IT literacy.

The proposed system provides reports in accordance to the Department of Health's Field Health Service Information System (FHSIS) such as family planning, maternity checkup, child vaccination, dental checkup (if applicable), infectious disease prevention and control services, environmental health and sanitation services, and non-communicable disease prevention and control services. This also serves as a reference for the collection of information needed from the citizens patronizing the services of their barangay's health center such as name, age, gender, date of birth parents/spouse details and the like including the disclosure agreement presented on the privacy notice.

The access to patient information is covered by role-based user privileges. This feature limits members of the barangay health services office to a specific extent in functions such as view, edit, update, and manipulate patient documents.

The communication line used for scheduling is only limited to a third-party app and google meet should the patient request for a video conference consultation. This may be changed upon the request of the existing barangay captain and barangay health administrator.

The proposed system does not cover inventory of medicines and other logistics covered by the barangay health services as per the agreed scope with the barangay health workers due to the versatility and inconsistency of supplies and human resource.

These considerations were highlighted for the development of an Online Health Services. This is implemented to two(2) barangay health services (Barangay Guitnang Bayan 1 and Barangay Sta. Ana) providers to be able to concretize adaptability that will make the system worthy of being used by other health centers in San Mateo Rizal.

1.1 Specific Objectives

To develop an Adaptable On-line Health Services System for the Barangays of San Mateo Rizal to improve patient monitoring and profiling for maternal, neonatal, TB treatment compliance, and other health services provided by the center. As well as collecting data and disseminating health information to policy makers, providers and citizens in an organized and secured manner. The detailed objective of the system are as follows:

To provide an adaptable health information system to the Barangay Health Centers of San Mateo Rizal that will help

provide uniformed documentations, report generation and patient records that correspond to the requirement of the Department of Health in subordination by the Municipal Health Office.

To lessen time consumed and rework in the process of patient profiling, enlistment and patient record updates. *Patient Profiling and enlistment* involves capturing of the patient's basic information such as name, contact details, address, occupation, birthdate, monthly income, number of living children (if applicable), name of spouse and spouse details.

To have safe, secure and easy access to patient records and information. Allowing barangay health officers to access information through an online system with less risk on possible effects of calamities such as flood and earthquake in consideration to the territories covered by the Municipality of San Mateo, Rizal.

To generate an online comparative report of diseases within the preferred time as well as to store operational data, communication data submitted to the Municipal Health Office, and documents.

To allow patient consultation on-line scheduling. Citizens of San Mateo Rizal do often visit the health centers with concerns directed to maternal and child check ups/vaccination, tuberculosis, hypertension, infectious disease and other non-communicable diseases. These visits were all based on the dosage required for patients for a vaccine or for monitoring. On-line scheduling will provide patients an overview of the barangay health office's schedule and may be catered to based on their preferred date and time.

To provide an online communication line between the patients and the barangay health officer through instant messaging for any related inquiries.

To have a role-based access for system users. Providing different privileges with stronger security features for the health information system. Patients will be provided with login and password credentials in reference to the existing list of barangay and barangay citizens. Nurses, midwives and other barangay health officers will also have different levels of access for the system.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Health Information System

According to the Design and Implementation of Health Information Systems by Theo Lippeveld ^[1], in their book Development and Implementation of Health Information Systems, under the subtitle of 'What is wrong with the current health information systems?', information systems tend to be data-driven rather than action-driven which then resulted in inadequate provision of the needed management support. It is where most healthcare providers in developing countries equate information systems with filling endless registers with names and addresses of patients, compiling information on diseases on certain periods of time without

adequate feedback. As expressed as well, the data received are often not congruence with the ideals of decision making due to incomplete, inaccurate, untimely, obsolete and unrelated to priority tasks and functions of the local health personnel. Which then leads to an assumption that health information systems are management obstacles rather than tools.

The referenced publication also itemized the reasons for the aforementioned statements into five points such as (1) irrelevance of the information gathered; (2) poor quality of data, this is without considering the technical skills of the health workers collecting the data; (3) duplication and waste among parallel health information systems, in reference to existing ones; (4) lack of timely reporting and feedback and (5) poor use of information.

Figure 1. Components of Health Information System by WHO

2.2 Access Efficiency

In the year 2016, Bingcong Zeng and Benjamin P. -C. Yen ^[2] evaluated user-system adaptability in the use of web based information systems through the model access efficiency. The proponents cited three common approaches for adaptation techniques such as: page splitting, content summary, and transcoding. *Page Splitting's* main idea is the division of original web pages into several sub-pages in order to fit user's specific requirements. *Content Summary* on the other hand allowed users to browse the summary of web pages before deciding to visit any page with full details. Lastly, *Transcoding* which is known as the approach in tailoring web content in accordance with the capabilities of the client device and the network connection.

The Access Efficiency model considered two factors: user and system side. For the system, it looked into the easiness of being accessed for web content and structure also known as "accessibility" which is in connection with the ability of a user to navigate through the system/website easily and comfortably through inlinks. Thus, incorporating attractiveness of the inlink and the level of its source page. During the process of adaptation, activities were evaluated and web structure as well as user interfaces are being changed in order to improve user experience.

2.3 Electronic Health Record Adaptability

and Interoperability

Knowledge management as cited by Michael Koenig [3] in his article is the 'process of capturing, distributing, and effectively using knowledge'. In this context, the Conceptual Healthcare Knowledge Management Model for Adaptability and Interoperability of Electronic Health records pointed out that knowledge management is important in guiding health care providers in working on new technology and in juicing out its benefits. The study also defined adaptability in various ways such as (1) patient's and clinician's acceptability (2) usability and user friendliness of the interface and (3) security and confidentiality of EHR. Also, user acceptance is salient for the development of an EHR. According to the study, patients will accept data if they are educated and aware of the use of EHR, know that the data is secured with smart interfaces to assist their queries and, if they have access to readily available computers or a network connection infrastructure. On the other hand, clinicians will accept the EHR if they realize its advantages, they are computer literate, find the user interface friendly, assured that data is secured and know that they are involved in the development process of EHR.

Figure 2. Knowledge Management Environment

2.4 Quality Model

The software quality model represents a hierarchical quality model which focuses on a wider range of characteristics introduced by B.W Boehm [4]. This model consists of *portability, reliability, efficiency, usability (human engineering), testability, understability and modifiability*.

Figure 3. Quality Model

2.5 The Philippine eHealth Strategic Guiding Principles

The Philippines eHealth development [5] guiding principles were laid down in nine items such as (1) client-focus or person centered information (2) collaboration and / or partnerships with different stakeholders (3) user's involvement (4) strategic approach in phases to achieve the eHealth vision so as to gain more focus, judiciously and efficiently use resources (5) harmonization and interdependence to guide alignment of eHealth activities at the national level without controlling health care providers to implement local eHealth solutions (6) recognize the presence of entities that have already started eHealth so as not to constraint their continuing advancement and gain their support (7) availability of human resource to implement the eHealth agenda in the country and promote transparency and public accountability (8) compliance to laws and regulations (9) optimize use of resources so as not to duplicate time, effort and investments

The Desired eHealth Outcomes.

This section in the published article for Philippines eHealth Strategic Framework and Plan for 2014-2020 also discussed the desired outcomes should the proposal become operational. The main context focuses on the both the Health System Goal or Challenge and the Desired eHealth Outcomes whereas:

Health System Goal or Challenge for Health Consumers : Safer and Quality Health Care.

This discusses the increase ability to access, control and share of health information, minimization of time and effort in providing the same health information to different health care providers. Also, the minimization of health inequalities of those living in remote or rural areas dues to poor access to health care and to address shortage of health human resource affecting those in remote or rural areas.

Desired eHealth Outcomes. The desired eHealth outcomes for the aforementioned goals or challenges were the improved access to health information and maintenance of the personal health record, with controlled access to personal health information, and improved management of health care plans. Then, improved access to primary care services for rural and remote locations that reduces travel time and access; improved access to knowledge, services and resources to assist in managing one's health with support for early detection and treatment of diseases, and better management of health conditions and adherence to medication and treatment regimes.

3 PROJECT STRUCTURE

3.1 Components

The proposed system is divided into multiple functionalities that is intended majority of the transactions performed in a barangay health services center to further help the barangay health workers. As such were also referred from the forms, documents and

roles of responsibilities made known to the proponent.

- Family Planning
- Maternity Checkup
- Child Vaccination
- Dental Checkup (if applicable)
- Infectious Disease Prevention and Control Services
- Non-communicable Disease Prevention and Control Services
- Environmental Health and Sanitation Services
- Online consultation scheduling
- Client and Barangay Health Worker Accounts
- Differentiated User level access

3.2 Conceptual Framework

Figure 4. Conceptual Framework of the Proposed Project

The conceptual framework of the proposed study starts by reducing rework within the transactions and services provided by the barangay health workers such as repeated patient profiling due to a number of forms to be accomplished despite minor consultations, duplication of forms which were reported as lost, and inability of the patient to return to consultation dates. This also includes patient account with security credentials, online messaging, fast report generation and adaptive user-system experience.

4 METHODOLOGY

4.1 Software Development Life Cycle

The Agile method for system development allows an iterative process of development and delivery. This also covers sprint planning where at the start of each development cycle or sprint, tasks are scheduled to be implemented and delivered. Then, a sprint review, where clients review the result and provide feedback. Agile is also defined as a systems development approach that includes values, principles, and practices useful for flexible, interactive and participative approach [6].

Figure 4. Agile Method

This method fits in the development procedure for Online Health Services System of barangays in San Mateo Rizal. Since one of the objective of the study is to be able to provide an adaptable system that will cater to any health services provider within the scope as stated, constant feedbacking is needed. Iterated evaluations coming from the clients were collected as often as necessary and applied to the system.

4.3 Collection of Data

Sample Size Determination

Barangay Guitnang Bayan 1 and Barangay Sta. Ana has a total population of 40,758 as of 2015 based on PhilAtlas [7]. Given this information, the determinant of survey respondents were based on two measures such as the margin of error (or confidence interval) and confidence level corresponding to a questionnaire as per the use of the proposed system.

The targeted confidence level to the proposed system was set to 95% as a standard in quantitative research as per the check market reference written by Gert Van Dessel (Dessel, 2013) and a 5 % margin of error. Thus, the completion of sample size required for the proposed system's adaptability and acceptance survey is 381 respondents while the estimated response rate is at 20%.

The same procedures were performed in determining the number of respondents for barangay health workers (BHWs). Each barangay has a total of 20 BHWs. Considering the 5% margin of error and the 95% confidence, the result is still 20 respondents. Thus, getting the 100% of barangay health workers population for barangay Guitnang Bayan 1 and Sta. Ana.

Further data collection such as interview and documents & records citation were performed at the start and during the development process to engage familiarity in the existing system's process.

Survey

The citations for user-system adaptability, quality model and knowledge management served as a reference in the development of the survey questionnaire as categorized by the following:

Reliability: Extent to which software performs according to requirements.

Usability (Human Engineering): Extent of effort required to learn, operate and understand functions of the software.

Understandability: Effort required for a user to recognize logical concept and its applicability.

Security: Encompasses a holistic restriction based on access in information from authentication to modification both internally and externally.

Support: Covers support for users of the proposed system in different levels and formats such as written materials, trainings and costs.

4.4 Procedure for the Calculation of Data

The proponent used the 5-point Likert Scale [6] to further represent how the respondents/clients agreed in the functions and features of the system as per the survey categories.

$$WM = \frac{\sum(w_i - N_i)}{n_x}$$

Where:

w=data set total
 N_i =sub criteria
 n_x =number of sub criteria

4.5 Testing Procedure

The testers were representatives for Barangays Guitnang Bayan 1 and Sta. Ana. Both parties applied the usual procedures while undergoing a parallel implementation of the proposed system.

Patient profiles were accomplished once by the clients and the rest of the documents were auto filled following the procedure of identifying the desired consultation.

Initial procedures were focused on child vaccination and maternity checkups. The system applied consultation updates since it is crucial to take note on the dates of patient visits especially for immunization.

Afterwards, sample reports were printed incorporating the activities noted on the same day. Stress test were also applied where navigation of multiple pages for the website were performed as well as correction of inputs as desired by the barangay health worker in charge within his/her user privileges.

Documentation, system and training modules and other related files for Online Health Services System were provided to the clients for testing.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this phase, the respondents were asked to evaluate the system based on the presented success indicators in reference to the standards of health information system components by the World Health Organization and the paradigm of roles and responsibilities from the House Bill 01339 by Hon. Luis Villafuerte Jr [8]. The nurses, midwives and barangay health workers for Barangays Guitnang Bayan 1 and Sta. Ana answered the survey evaluation. The data that were gathered were arranged, computed and analyzed to be acceptable and adaptable. Responses from both barangays, patients and health workers were categorized as per reliability, usability, understandability, security and support.

5.1 Project Evaluation

Tables 1 and 2 shows the respondents' weighted mean in consideration of the categories of success indicators from Barangay Guitnang Bayan 1 and Barangay Sta. Ana's barangay health workers.

CRITERIA	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
Reliability	4.63	Very Adaptable
Usability	4.4	Very Adaptable
Understandability	4.18	Very Adaptable
Security	4.5	Very Adaptable
Support	4.57	Very Adaptable

Table 1. Summary of Mean for System Evaluation of Brgy. Guitnang Bayan 1's BHW

CRITERIA	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
Reliability	4.38	Very Adaptable
Usability	4.31	Very Adaptable
Understandability	4.42	Very Adaptable
Security	4.58	Very Adaptable
Support	4.37	Very Adaptable

Table 2. Summary of Mean for System Evaluation of Brgy. Sta. Ana's BHW

Table 3 and 4 shows the respondents' weighted mean in consideration of the categories of success indicators from Barangay Guitnang Bayan 1 and Barangay Sta. Ana's patients.

CRITERIA	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
Reliability	4.29	Very Adaptable
Usability	4.15	Very Adaptable
Understandability	4.14	Very Adaptable
Security	4.36	Very Adaptable

Table 3. Summary of Mean for System Evaluation of Brgy. Sta. Ana's Patients

CRITERIA	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
Reliability	3.99	Very Adaptable
Usability	4.07	Very Adaptable
Understandability	4.20	Very Adaptable
Security	3.61	Very Adaptable

Table 4. Summary of Mean for System Evaluation of

6 CONCLUSION

The opportunities identified prior to the development and implementation of an online health services systems for barangay as an adaptive health information system proves to be achievable based on the responses of the clients/patients. Both barangay in San Mateo Rizal, Guitnang Bayan 1 and Sta. Ana were able to test and attest the functionalities of the proposed system. The respondents were able to manipulate the system with less supervision and provide reports based on the Field Health Services Information System (FHSIS) as per the policy and guidelines of the department of health.

The automated computation of transactions per category per day were able to provide reports per month. Correct and accurate numbers appeared as observed based on the number of patient consultations which increases reliability.

Nurses, midwives and the barangay health workers, were able to use the system based on the credentials (username and password) they were registered into and maximize the level of usability as per security permission.

The flow of navigation for the proposed system matched the existing system based on the evaluation of both patients and barangay health workers given a mean of 4.18 for Barangay Guitnang Bayan 1's BHW evaluation and 4.42 for Barangay Sta. Ana. While, a mean of 4.14 and 4.20 as per understanding the system manifested from the patients of both barangays. Thus strengthening the adaptable functionalities of the proposed system.

Security was highlighted in the development of the system by initially providing two (2) Data Sharing Agreement for the barangay health workers and the municipal health office and patients. This gives both parties a reliable documentation that there is a clear understanding regarding the transition of data from the patient to the barangay health service providers and the municipal health office. Also, each user was given strict credentials whose validity primarily extends up to the enlistment of their barangay. The super admin also has the privilege of limiting access within the users, manage/remove a suspicious accounts and degree of qualifications in the disposal of inactive health records.

In this context, the success indicators, whose purpose is to address the different applications for adaptability were achieved.

As per the user-system adaptability study of Zeng and Yen mainly for the navigational features and usability of the proposed system both agreed to be very evident in the context of the user/respondents. Then, the electronic health record adaptability and interoperability adhering to knowledge management were also established throughout the development and implementation of the system. This is through constant consultation and feedbacking - agile method, knowledge management - by educating the users through trainings, and creation of learning modules, and addressing multiple *How's* in the system functionalities.

These aspects were encapsulated through the quality model by B.W. Boehm. Having satisfactorily reached a very acceptable mean for each item on the success indicator and the ability of users coming from two (2) barangays to use the proposed Online Health Services System including patients has proven the user-system adaptability.

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